

Milestone: MS8 - Revised Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers

Lead Participant: Health-RI

Author: WP8

Due: 31.08.2025

Date of Completion:

Means of Verification

[Milestone report](#)

[Revised requirements table](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

no

Project participants & others

EMBL, CRG, BSC, CESSDA, GESIS, UKDS, TARKI, ECRIN, UiO, HDR UK, UNIVDUN, Turku UAS, CSC, Sigma2, ODISSEI, SURF

Next action steps

- Report on Milestone during 2nd Evaluation & Adoption workshop in Bergen, NO
- Finalize prototypes
- Organize 2nd Blueprint validation workshop (online)